

Aluminothermic reduction: a sustainable method for producing Fe₆₅Si₂₆B₉ phase change material

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ABSTRACT: Fe₆₅Si₂₆B₉ (wt.%) is proposed to be a high-temperature phase change material (PCM) for a thermal energy storage system, due to its high latent heat of fusion and minimal volume change during solidification. Currently, the production of Fe₆₅Si₂₆B₉ alloy involves mixing FeSi alloys with either pure boron (B) or FeB alloys. The use of pure boron is high cost, while the carbothermic reduction of FeB alloy results in significant greenhouse gas emissions and high energy consumption. In this regard, the aluminothermic reduction is proposed to use FeSi alloys, aluminum and iron metals, and calcinated colemanite for producing this FeSiB PCM. According to the experimental results, the equilibrium is achieved after 3h holding at temperatures range from 1550°C to 1650°C. By varying the slag/metal (S/M) ratio from 0.6 to 1.4, the boron content in the FeSiB alloys can be increased from 5.2wt.% to 15wt.% after 3h holding at 1650°C. Maintaining the S/M ratio at 1, the produced FeSiB alloys exhibit a B content between 9-13 wt.%, Si and Fe ranging in 24-30wt.% and 61-64wt.%, respectively. The theoretical energy consumption is estimated to be around 1182kWh/t metal. Therefore, aluminothermic reduction can be an efficient method for producing FeSiB alloys.

Keywords:

FeSiB

B₂O₃

Aluminothermic

PCM

Thermal Energy Storage

1. Introduction

Thermal Energy Storage (TES) is a critical technology to reduce the dependence on fossil fuels and achieve net zero emission by 2050 [1]. It manages the intermittency of renewable sources, such as solar and wind, by storing excess energy for later use. Among various TES techniques, thermophotovoltaic (TPV) techniques stands out for their ability to convert heat directly into electrical energy [2]. This innovative TES system requires higher operational temperatures to improve energy transition efficiency, as higher temperatures facilitate more efficient energy storage system. However, current TES technologies primarily use materials with melting temperatures below 1000 °C [3]. This limitation comes from a low thermal stability at higher temperatures of commonly used materials (like molten salts and their hydrates). In this regard, a promising high temperature phase change material (PCM), Fe₆₅Si₂₆B₉ eutectic alloy (65wt.% iron, 26wt.% silicon,

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and 9wt.% boron), has been identified as exhibiting a suitable melting temperature (1220°C) and a high latent heat of fusion (>1 MWh/m³) [4]–[11]. The main concept behind designing this alloy is: (i) to add boron to provide even higher latent heat of fusion, and (ii) to introduce iron to reduce undesired volumetric expansion upon liquid/solid transition. Consequently, the alloy shows the highest energy storage density among the reported high temperature PCMs. Furthermore, unlike silicon [12], this alloy exhibits a lack of volumetric expansion during solidification, which is critical for avoiding crucible damage during thermal cycling.

However, a wide scale implementation of the Fe₆₅Si₂₆B₉ high temperature PCM meets some serious technical and practical obstacles that ought to be faced. The previous fabrication method of this alloy in the lab is based on melting ferrosilicon (FeSi) alloys with either pure boron or ferroboration (FeB) alloys at temperatures up to 1750 °C [13]. Both methods are costly and high energy consuming, which is not economically and environmentally sustainable.

To address these issues, the Thermobat project, funded by the European Commission, proposes a novel approach to producing the optimal FeSiB PCM using cost-effective raw and waste materials through the aluminothermic reduction method. It benefits from the exothermic nature of the reaction between aluminum and B₂O₃, leading to a lower energy consumption. The process starts with mixing FeSi, iron, and aluminum metal, and B₂O₃-based oxides at high temperatures, and ending with a production of molten mixture of FeSiB alloys with aluminum content maintained below 1wt.% and a by-product of Al₂O₃-based slag. Besides, the raw materials can be sourced from abundant and waste materials, such as aluminum dross, iron scraps, silicon kerf-loss waste, discarded FeSi and silicon fines. Hence, this process is expected to offer a cost-efficient way to manufacture the optimal FeSiB alloys.

This study aims to optimize the FeSiB alloy production process. It starts by establishing the experimental process through thermodynamic analyses. Following this, the study investigates the effect of different process parameters, such as the operating temperature, the holding time, and the initial ratio of slag to metal, on the amount of boron in the produced FeSiB alloys.

2. Experimental Procedure

In the production of FeSiB alloy through aluminothermic reduction method, the raw materials used include FeSi75, Al, and Fe metals, and commercial colemanite (CaO·2B₂O₃·5H₂O). FeSi75 and Al (99.9999wt.%) metals were sourced from Finnjord AS and Hydro in Norway, respectively. Fe metal (99.99wt.%) was purchased from Alfa Aesar. The commercial colemanite powder (particle size < 75µm) was provided by Eti Maden company[14]. Notably, the colemanite required a preliminary calcination step at 500–600°C for 180min to remove its crystal water. The chemical composition of the calcinated colemanite was further analyzed using Inductively Coupled Plasma Sector Field Mass Spectrometry (ICP-SFMS), as shown in **Table 1**.

The experiments were conducted in either a resistance furnace or an induction furnace under an argon (99.999% Ar) atmosphere. The BN-coated SiC crucibles were used to prevent the creeping of oxides, due to their good wetting behavior. 8-90g calcinated colemanite and 8-90g Fe₅₅Si₂₂Al₂₃ master alloys were placed in the crucibles with the oxides layered above the master alloys. It is noted that the Fe₅₅Si₂₂Al₂₃ master alloys were produced by mixing Fe-75Si, Al, and Fe metals in an induction furnace at 1650°C under Ar atmosphere. The crucibles with different initial Slag/Metal (S/M) ratio raw materials were maintained for a duration of 60 or 180min in the temperature range of 1550-1650°C, aiming to find the optimal parameters for producing the desired FeSiB alloy.

After experiments, the chemical composition of the produced FeSiB alloys was analyzed using ICP-

SFMS. The microstructures and phases present within the alloys were examined using Electron Probe Micro-Analysis (EPMA) and wavelength dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (WDS), respectively. The thermodynamic behaviors were assessed by FactSage 8.1, using FactPS, FTlite, and FToxide databases. Additionally, the energy consumption of the process was estimated using the Heat and Material Balance module of HSC Chemistry 9 software.

Table 1 Chemical compositions of calcinated colemanite (wt.%)

Main oxides	B ₂ O ₃	CaO	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	MgO
Composition	55.7	35.0	5.0	0.2	0.1	4.0

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Aluminothermic reduction using colemanite

Colemanite can be used to produce FeSiB PCM in a single step via the aluminothermic reduction method. The process, depicted in Fig. 1, is designed based on thermodynamic analysis by FactSage 8.1 using the FTlite and FToxide databases. By reacting Fe55Si22Al23 with calcinated colemanite at 1600 °C, the desired alloy (Fe65Si24B11) can be produced, alongside a by-product consisting of 21wt.% B₂O₃. The Al content in the target alloy is reduced to 0.35wt.% at equilibrium state.

Notably, the initial Fe65Si26B9 eutectic alloy, as mentioned before, was designed by FactSage 7.2 using the FTlite database [4]. However, the subsequent experiments indicated that the actual alloy composition was close to, but not exactly at the eutectic point [11]. The Fe61Si29B10 alloy was later considered as the eutectic alloy based on the phase distribution observed in the eutectic structures [11]. Subsequently, by using a new version of FactSage 8.1 for the thermodynamic analyses, the eutectic composition was changed to Fe65Si24B11. This suggests that the eutectic composition lies in the range of 61-65wt.% Fe, 24-29wt.% Si, and 9-11wt.% B.

To validate this process, experiments are conducted in an argon atmosphere with a holding time of 3 hours at 1650 °C. The chemical composition of the produced FeSiB alloy was between 62-63wt.% Fe, 24-26wt.% Si, 10.2-11.8wt.%B and 0.5-0.7wt.%Al, which had a good agreement with the predicted equilibrium compositions.

Fig. 2 shows the microstructure and elemental mapping of the produced Fe62Si25B11.8 alloy. The primary phases, comprising FeB, FeSi, SiB_n, and FeSiB₃, were aligned with those reported in our previous publications [4], [5], [11], [13], [15], [16]. Additionally, AlB₁₂ phases were detected in the alloy. Notably, it is difficult to distinguish the SiB_n and AlB₁₂ phases, as seen from Fig. 2b, due to boron being a major component. However, approximately 3.5wt.% AlB₁₂ phases was calculated to be presented in the produced FeSiB alloys based on the analyzed Al content (0.5-0.7wt.%) after solidification.

Fig. 1. Flow chat for the production of FeSiB alloy via aluminothermic reduction using colemanite.

Fig. 3 presents the elemental mapping at the interface between the Fe₆₂Si₂₅B_{11.8} alloy and the slag. According to the elemental distributions, the main elements were Al, Si, Ca, and O in the slag phase. The chemical composition of the slag was further analyzed by ICP-SFMS, summarized in Fig. 4. A comparison of oxides compositions before and after experiments revealed that the B₂O₃ content decreased to ~25wt.% from 56wt.%, and the Al₂O₃ content increased to ~34wt.% from 0.2wt.%. The CaO and SiO₂ levels remained relatively unchanged. These findings are in good agreement with the equilibrium content predicted by FactSage 8.1. Hence, it is believed that the reaction reached equilibrium after 3h holding at 1650°C with an initial slag/metal ratio of 1.

Fig. 2. (a) Microstructural features of Fe_{62.3}Si_{24.6}B_{11.8} alloy, and (b) its EPMA elemental mapping.

Fig. 3. EPMA elemental mapping at the interface between FeSiB alloy and the produced slag.

Fig. 4. Comparative analysis of the chemical composition in slags.

3.2. Effect of operating temperature

The effect of operating temperature on the boron content within the produced FeSiB alloys is investigated. In the experiments, the added calcinated colemanite and FeSiB master alloy were combined in a 1:1 ratio and subjected to a 3h holding time at 1550°C, 1600°C, and 1650°C, respectively. The analyzed boron contents in the produced FeSiB alloys are presented in Fig. 5. It is observed that the boron content was higher at 1550°C (12.6wt.%) compared to 1600°C (9.8wt.% ± 1.3wt.%), however at 1650°C it was increased again (10.8wt.% ± 0.8wt.%). This suggest that the standard variation is quite high and that a temperature between 1500-1650 °C is a good range. According to the thermodynamic databases, a lower temperature favors the aluminothermic reduction duo to its exothermic characteristics. When the experimental data is compared to the predicted equilibrium boron content, it is seen that the boron content has a good agreement with the predicted equilibrium content, indicating that equilibrium was reached after 3h holding time at temperatures 1550-1650°C. However, the experimental result was higher than the predicted equilibrium value at 1550°C, which is unreasonable. This discrepancy could be due to limitations within the FactSage database (FTlite + FToxide). Nonetheless, it shows that the chemical reaction rate is independent of the operating temperature in the range of 1550-1650°C.

Fig. 5. The effect of temperature on boron content in the produced FeSiB alloys, the rectangles present the experimental results, and the triangles represent the predicted equilibrium results (FTlite + FToxide).

3.3. Effect of holding time

The effect of holding time on boron content in FeSiB alloys produced through aluminothermic reduction is studied. In these experiments, the calcinated colemanite was reacted with Fe55Si22Al23 master alloy with the initial S/M ratio of 1 at 1650°C for the holding time of 60min and 180min, respectively. It is seen from Fig. 6 that the boron content was increased from 5wt.% to up to 11.8wt.% as the holding time extended from 60min to 180min. The aluminothermic reduction occurred at the interface between the molten alloy and molten slag, resulting in boron transferring into the alloy and Al_2O_3 forming in the slag. It might indicate that the aluminothermic reduction is mainly affected by the mass transfer at the interface. The slag's viscosity, which played a critical role in mass transfer, was predicted using FactSage 8.1 with the Melts database. It is found that the viscosity was increased from 0.35 poise for the initial calcinated colemanite to 1.20 poise in the final equilibrium slag at this temperature. The formation of Al_2O_3 during the process contributed to a higher viscosity, leading to a more viscous slag within the system. Consequently, in scenarios where stirring is not employed, it is recommended to maintain a holding time of 3h to optimize the reaction. However, by actively stirring the slag and molten alloy at the holding temperature, it has the possibility to reduce the holding time needed to achieve equilibrium.

Fig. 6. The effect of holding time on boron content in the produced FeSiB alloys.

3.4. Effect of the initial S/M ratio

The effect of the initial S/M ratio on the boron content in the alloys is also studied. For this purpose, the raw materials were charged at an initial S/M ratios varying from 0.6 to 1.4 and subjected to a holding time of 3h at 1650°C. Subsequently, the elemental composition of the produced FeSiB alloys, including boron, aluminum, silicon, and iron, was analyzed using ICP-SFMS and was summarized in Fig. 7, where the dashed lines present the expected ideal elemental contents, assuming complete consumption of aluminum in the reaction with B₂O₃ oxide.

It is seen from Fig. 7d that the aluminum content was consistently below 1.2wt.% in the produced alloys across the range of the initial S/M ratios, suggesting that the aluminum element was almost complete consumed during the process. Then, Fig. 7c reveals that the iron content in the alloys was relatively constant and had a good agreement with its predicted ideal content. It implies that iron did not participate in any reactions.

Then, Fig. 7a and b show that there was an observed increase in boron content by the increase in the initial S/M ratio, while the silicon content displayed the opposite way. The experimental results of boron and silicon had a good agreement at the initial S/M ratio of 1, indicating that the aluminothermic reduction was limited to B₂O₃ oxides. With the initial S/M ratio under 1, the boron content was lower than the predicted amount, and the silicon content exceeded the predicted amount. It suggested that the aluminum reacted with both B₂O₃ and SiO₂ oxides, where the latter came from the charged calcinated colemanite (Table 1). In contrast, with the initial S/M ratios above 1, the boron content was higher than the predicted amount and the silicon content was lower than the predicted amount. It indicated that the boron was contributed from both silicothermic and aluminothermic reductions.

Therefore, the initial S/M ratio not only affected the boron content in the produced alloys but also affected the consumption of silicon in the raw materials. Hence, an initial S/M ratio close to 1 was recommended to optimize the reduction processes and the final alloy composition.

Fig. 7. The effect of initial Slag/Metal (S/M) ratio on the chemical composition of the produced FeSiB alloys. (a): Boron, (b): Aluminum, (c): Silicon, and (d): Iron. The spots represent the experimental results. The dashed lines represent the predicted equilibrium contents with complete aluminothermic reduction.

3.5. Energy balance

To manufacture 1 ton Fe₆₄Si₂₅B₁₁ alloy, 1.16 tons calcinated colemanite and 1.16 tons Fe₅₅Si₂₂Al₂₃ alloy are required, and a by-product of 1.32 tons slag is produced after reacting at 1600°C. It is noted that this assumption is calculated by FactSage 8.1 using FTlite and FToxide databases under equilibrium state. The distribution of oxides and metal elements are listed in **Table 2**. Further estimation of electrical energy consumption is conducted using HSC Chemistry software (version 9). Notably, the calculation is based on the principle of enthalpy conservation that the sum of enthalpy in input materials and electrical energy must be equal to the enthalpy in the output products. Then, the energy flow for producing 1 ton Fe₆₄Si₂₅B₁₁ alloy is illustrated in the Sankey diagram (Fig. 8). It is observed that the energy input from the metal was slightly higher than the energy in the output metal, due to the exothermic reaction between aluminum and B₂O₃ oxide. The electrical energy (1182kWh/t of metal) is directly converted into heat in the output metal and slag. Hence, the aluminothermic reduction process for Fe₆₄Si₂₅B₁₁ alloy proves to be energy efficient. Additionally, one may recover some of the heat in the slag and metal during cooling which is totally 1422 kWh/ton, and with an energy yield of 20% around 300 kWh/ton could be recycled.

Table 2 Mass balance of the production of 1 ton Fe₆₄Si₂₅B₁₁ through aluminothermic reduction process

Raw Materials (kg, 25°C)		Slag (kg, 1600°C)		output metal (kg, 1600°C)	
CaO	406	CaO	406		
SiO ₂	58	SiO ₂	84		
MgO	46	MgO	46		
B ₂ O ₃	650	B ₂ O ₃	290		
		Al ₂ O ₃	495		
Si	255			Si	245
Al	267			Al	4
Fe	638			Fe	639
				B	112

Fig. 8. Sankey diagram, illustrating the energy flow to produce 1 ton Fe₆₄Si₂₅B₁₁ alloy by the reaction between Fe₅₅Si₂₂Al₂₃ and calcinated colemanite at 1600°C with an initial S/M ratio of 1. Thermal loss is not included in the calculation.

4. Conclusions

This research focuses on developing a production method for FeSiB alloy for the use in a thermal energy storage system. The optimal composition is in the range of 61-65wt.% iron, 24-29wt.% silicon, and 9-11wt.% boron. In this regard, the aluminothermic reduction method is chosen, where calcinated colemanite and Fe₅₅Si₂₂Al₂₃ master alloys are used as the primary raw materials. To achieve the desired FeSiB alloy composition, the study investigates the effect of various parameters on the boron content of the produced alloys. According to the experimental results, the raw materials should be charged with an initial Slag/Metal ratio close to 1, and then subjected to the temperatures ranging from 1550°C to 1650°C for approximately 3h. The estimated energy consumption is around 1182kWh/t metal. These finding is important for establishing an environmentally friendly and energy-efficient method to produce the optimal FeSiB alloys.

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